

Sensitivity of X-, C- and L-band SAR backscatter to burn severity in mediterranean pine forests

Mihai Tanase¹, Maurizio Santoro², Juan de la Riva¹, Fernando Pérez -Cabello¹ and Thuy Le Toan³
¹ *University of Zaragoza, Dpt. of Geography, Pedro Cerbuna 12, Zaragoza, 50009, Spain, mihai.tanase@tma.ro,*

² *Gamma Remote Sensing AG, Gümligen, Switzerland*

³ *Centre d'Etudes Spatiales de la Biosphère, Toulouse, France*

Abstract

Synthetic aperture radar (SAR) data at X-, C- and L-band have been investigated to determine the relationship between backscatter and forest burn severity over three sites in Spain. The dependency of the SAR backscatter upon local incidence angle and environmental conditions has been analyzed. At HH and VV polarizations the backscatter increased with burn severity for X- and C-band whereas for L-band it decreased. Cross-polarized (HV) backscatter decreased with burn severity for all frequencies. The sensitivity of the co-polarized backscatter to burn severity decreased for increasing local incidence angle for all frequencies except at L-band. Determination coefficients were used to quantify the relationship between radar backscatter and burn severity for given intervals of local incidence angle. For X- and C-band co-polarized data higher determination coefficients were observed for slopes oriented towards the sensors whereas for cross-polarized data the determination coefficients were higher for slopes oriented away from the sensor. At L-band the association strength of cross-polarized data to burn severity was high for all local incidence angles. C- and L-band cross-polarized backscatter showed better potential for burn severity estimation in the Mediterranean environment when the local incidence angle is accounted for. The small dynamic range observed for X-band data could hinder its use in forests affected by fires.

I. INTRODUCTION

The high number of forest fires occurring every year constitutes one of the major degradation factors of the Mediterranean ecosystems. On average, half million hectares are annually burnt in the European part of the Mediterranean basin making fires an important environmental problem. Fire occurrence alteration during the last decades closely reflects socio-economic changes in the traditional land use and lifestyle which implied the abandonment of large areas of farmland leading to recovery of vegetation [1] and an increased pressure from tourism activities [2].

Forest fires are an important source of atmospheric aerosols and green-house gases, causal relationship between biomass burning and interannual variability of related emissions being observed [3]. Severity indicates the way fire impacts the ecosystem and has significant effects on gas emission from burned areas [4], fire duration and intensity being the primary factors controlling the amount of released gases. The effects of fire on ecosystems are nowadays expressed by burn severity indexes usually defined as the degree of the environmental change. The composite burn index (CBI) provides a continuous scale between 0.0 (unburned) and 3.0 (highest burn severity) which summarizes the average burn condition of a forest plot. Usually, the field assessment of burn severity is carried out on a 15 m radius using a hierarchical sampling design. Each vegetation stratum is scored separately and the results are averaged for the entire plot [5].

The difficulty associated with the collection of extensive information on burn severity implies that remote sensing imagery is considered to assess the effect of fire in forests. One of the most

widely employed spectral index for burn severity assessment is the normalized burn ratio (NBR) [5] used in a bi-temporal approach with pre- and post-fire datasets (dNBR). The NBR index combines reflectance of near and shortwave infrared {1} whereas dNBR uses the difference between pre- and post-fire datasets {2} to isolate burned areas and to provide a quantitative measure of change with respect to the pre-fire status, unburned areas retaining values close to zero (i.e. -100 to 100).

$$NBR = (R4-R7) / (R4+R7) \{1\}$$

$$dNBR = NBR_{pre-fire} - NBR_{post-fire} \{2\}$$

where R is per pixel reflectance for Landsat TM bands.

With increasing severity dNBR values increase reaching the upper limit (i.e. 1000 to 1300) for extremely burned areas. Generally, empirical modeling is used to correlate dNBR to CBI field estimates of burn severity. The method is routinely used for burn severity mapping and provides accurate results in most of the environments, from boreal to mediterranean forests [6-9]. Nevertheless, reflectance based indices often fail to produce accurate results [10-12]. These indices use mostly indirect properties of the burned areas such as: near infrared reflectance decrease due to loss of healthy green vegetation; short-wave infrared reflectance increase due to less moisture content of vegetation and soils, increased substrate exposure and the presence of charred fuels. These properties are stable for unburned or highly burned areas but become inconsistent for intermediate severity levels where multiple effects combine. Some studies found it problematic to discriminate intermediate severity burns [13]. Reflectance based indices are also sensitive to plant phenology and solar elevation, so that monitoring severity trends over time or across regions can be subject to errors [14].

For studying fire effects in forested areas complementary information might be provided by SAR data since the backscattered signal contains information related to the vegetation structure and biomass [15]. For wavelengths of the order of few centimeters (X- and C- bands) scattering from the upper part of the tree crown is the predominant component of forest backscatter. The contribution of the understory and the forest floor is influenced primarily by the canopy architecture. For mediterranean species the first 30 cm of the crown contain most of the foliage biomass. In addition, relative water content of the leaves is higher than of woody parts in the upper part of the crown [16]. The high density of leaves and their relative high water content may therefore prevent the penetration of the high frequency waves to the lower layers of woody parts and soil [17] which may have high backscattering potential as suggested by [18]. Lower frequency L-band waves (23 cm) penetrate to a higher extent the canopy, interacting more with the large branches, tree stems or the forest floor [19]. Removal of leaves and branches by fire induces a decrease of backscatter from the canopy. Fire also increases soil exposure which could be used to estimate burn severity when using co-polarized channels. However, the destruction of the vegetation canopy makes the radar measurements sensitive to the state of the underlying ground [20] which results in backscatter dependency not only on the forest parameters but also on the soil moisture and roughness.

The impact of fire on the backscattering coefficient was found to cause ambiguous effects. Strong backscatter decrease was found for burned tropical forests at C-band VV polarization under dry weather conditions due to the decreased volume scattering and increased heat flux which led to a dryer ground [21, 22]. After rainfall the backscatter increased, discrimination from the unburned surrounding forests being difficult [23]. For temperate forests lower backscatter was found in fire affected areas [24] at C- and L-band (HV polarization) than for the adjacent unburned forest whereas for burned Australian woodlands and open forests L-band backscatter increased for co-

polarized and decreased for cross-polarized waves [25]. In boreal forests higher backscatter values than for the adjacent unburned areas were observed at C-band VV polarization when soil moisture was high due to poor soil drainage [26-29] whereas lower backscatter was observed for sites with better drainage conditions [29]. Finally, for mediterranean forests [30] found that post-fire C-band co-polarized backscattering coefficient increased independently of the accumulated precipitation index. However, the scenes characterized by wet conditions at acquisition presented higher backscatter levels than those acquired under dry conditions. Changes in the backscatter level appear to be strongly related to changes in soil moisture [31] data acquired after rainfall being less suitable for classification [32, 33] or forest biophysical parameters retrieval [34]. However, some fire related studies reported increased differentiation after rainfall for mediterranean burn scars [35]. All reported studies focused primarily on fire detection and mapping using SAR data. The potential of radar for estimating burn severity in forest has been reported in [24, 29, 36]. However, no extensive study on this topic is available in the literature according to our knowledge.

A major issue when using SAR images for thematic mapping and retrieval of biophysical parameters is represented by the local topography. Its influence on the backscattering coefficient is more pronounced for co-polarized beams and longer wavelengths, small tilt of terrain changing the scattering mechanism [37]. At low incidence angles the proportion of surface scattering to the total backscatter is larger compared to volume scattering [38]. Even for mild topography the backscattering coefficient is still altered and the radar signal needs to be compensated [39]. Topography also influences the backscattering coefficient from burned areas, sensor facing slopes appearing brighter than slopes oriented away from the sensor. Small local incidence angles were required for discriminating burned areas in a hilly Mediterranean region using co-polarized C-band data [35].

This work builds upon a first investigation on the signatures of fire affected areas using X-band backscatter data [40]. The promising results on burn severity estimation using a dual-polarized TerraSAR-X backscatter dataset suggested looking at lower frequencies, which can be assumed to be more sensitive to fire parameters because of the higher sensitivity of the backscattered signal to forest structural properties. In the following sections, the relationship between SAR backscatter acquired at C- and L-band is considered. For completeness, X-band data is also considered. Scope of this paper is to provide a comprehensive overview on burn severity evaluation and estimation from SAR backscatter for typical mediterranean forests. The specific objectives of the study were to:

1. evaluate the backscatter response in relation to burn severity for X-, C- and L-band data;
2. assess the role of the local topography and environmental conditions at acquisition on the backscatter coefficient;
3. infer the prediction power of the backscatter for burn severity estimation.

II. STUDY AREA

Three burn scars located in the central Ebro valley near Zuera town, Zaragoza province, Spain were the focus of this study. The area is characterized by Mediterranean climate and moderate topography elevation ranging from 500 to 750 m above sea level on slopes below 30°. The dominant land cover is forest interspersed with agricultural fields. Forests extend on approximately 22,000 hectares and are mainly formed by *Pinus halepensis* Mill. *Quercus coccifera* represented the main understory species. The structure of the forest was homogeneous more than 85% of the trees being in the codominant stratum. About 50% of the trees are 35 to 55 years old, 75% of them

being less than 65 years old. The average number of trees per hectare is 440 with a maximum of 2900 trees/ha and a minimum of 20 trees/ha in open areas. Forest average height is around 6.5 m and the average biomass around 45 tons/ha. Old stands reach heights of 12-13 m and 90 tons/ha.

At the first site (Zuera95) approximately 3,100 ha of forests burned between 23rd and 25th of June 1995 after a spark from a farming tractor ignited the vegetation next to the pine forest. In the adjacent second site (Zuera08) the fire ignited after a traffic accident. Around 2,200 ha of forests burned between 6th and 16th of August 2008. A third fire (Jaulin09) located approximately 60 km south, ignited due to a lightning storm on 21st of July 2009 and burned approximately 1,800 hectares. Fig. 1 gives an overview of the area affected by the fires. Burn severity expressed by means of dNBR was overlaid on the pre-fire Landsat TM image using the intervals proposed in [5]. Most of the forest was affected by high burn severity. Moderate and low severity areas are located mostly close to the perimeter of the forest where firefighters were able to control the fire spread.

III. DATA SETS

A. Satellite observations

The SAR images available to this study were acquired by the European Remote Sensing (ERS) SAR, the Environmental Satellite (ENVISAT) Advanced SAR (ASAR), the Advanced Land Observing Satellite (ALOS) Phased Array type L-band SAR (PALSAR) and the TerraSAR-X (TSX) SAR. In Table I the main characteristics of the radar sensors and processing parameters are provided. The datasets were delivered as single look complex (SLC) or precision (PRI) images. For each site a pair of Landsat TM images was used to estimate burn severity levels by means of dNBR index.

For the oldest fire scar (Zuera95) only ERS SAR 1/2 images were available (Table II). To study the consequence of rainfall on the backscatter coefficient ERS SAR images (23° look angle) were ordered for dates with and without precipitation. The matching Landsat TM scenes were acquired on March, 28 (pre-fire) and August, 3 (post-fire) 1995. Information on the geometric correction, calibration, atmospheric correction and topographic normalization of the Landsat scenes is given in [41].

For the Zuera08 site images from all satellites were available allowing the assessment of the backscatter coefficient response to burn severity at different SAR frequencies and polarizations (Table II). Dual-polarization TerraSAR-X dataset was acquired in dual-polarization strip map (SM) mode. ENVISAT ASAR images were acquired in the single-polarization imaging mode (IM) and in the dual-polarization alternating polarization (AP) mode. The ALOS PALSAR image was acquired in polarimetric (PLR) mode. TerraSAR-X data were available for two nominal incidence angles (i.e. 25° and 40°) whereas ERS SAR, ENVISAT ASAR and ALOS PALSAR data were available only for 22° to 26° nominal incidence angles (Table II). The Landsat TM images for the Zuera08 site were acquired on July 21, 2008 (pre-fire) and August 22, 2008 (post-fire). Subsets of the Landsat scenes were calibrated, atmospherically corrected and orthorectified using a linear polynomial model and incorporating information of the local topography. Detailed information regarding the processing of the Landsat TM scenes is given in [40]. Fig. 2 shows the burned area using a composite of backscatter (HH and HV) and their ratio at each SAR frequency. The fire scar can be easily distinguished from the surrounding forests. The green areas correspond to high cross-polarized (HV) backscatter, which is characteristic for dense vegetation. The blue/purple areas correspond to high co-polarized (HH) and little cross-polarized backscatter typically found in areas with no or low vegetation. The fire scar was characterized at all frequencies by increased co-

polarized and reduced cross-polarized backscatter when compared to adjacent unburned forest. Inside the fire perimeter zones affected by lower burn severity can be distinguished especially towards the borders.

One image at each frequency was available for the Jaulin09 site. The images were acquired at different nominal incidence angles. The TerraSAR-X image was acquired at 40° . The ENVISAT ASAR image was acquired at 23° whereas ALOS PALSAR fine beam dual polarization (FBD) image was acquired at 39° . The Landsat TM images were acquired on 2009.06.22 (pre-fire) and 2009.09.26 (post-fire) and were processed using the same method as for the Zuera08 site.

SAR data were absolutely calibrated using the calibration factors provided by the processing facilities and multi-looked to obtain the desired 25 m pixel size. To express the speckle reduction achieved after multi-looked, the number of statistically independent looks was estimated by means of the equivalent number of looks (ENL) [42] using forested areas not affected by fires (Table I). All SAR images were geocoded to Universal Transverse Mercator (UTM) projection using a digital elevation model (DEM) with 20 m pixel spacing which was resampled to 25 m for the analysis. Geocoding was based on a lookup table describing the transformation between the radar and the map geometry [43, 44] which was generated based on the DEM and the orbital information of the SAR sensors. A refinement step was applied to correct for the possible inaccuracies of the orbital state vectors. The offsets between SAR image and a reference SAR image simulated from the DEM were estimated using a cross-correlation algorithm. A simple linear model was derived to improve the original lookup table. To correct for the radiometric distortions introduced by the rough topography normalization for the varying incidence angle from near to far range and the effective pixel area was applied [45]. As a result images in gamma nought (γ°) format that only includes variations of the scattering properties of a target due to the local orientation were obtained.

B. In situ measurements of burn severity and ancillary datasets

CBI plots were established in high-severity, moderate-severity and low-severity areas inside Zuera08 and Jaulin09 fire perimeters. Burn severity was evaluated, as described in [46], using the magnitude of environmental change at each site with respect to the presumed pre-fire state. Detailed information on CBI plots assessment together with photos illustrating the main burn severity levels at Zuera08 site are given in [40]. To aid the interpretation, meteorological data collected from nearby meteorological stations were provided by the Spanish national meteorological agency (AEMET). The daily maximum and minimum temperature and precipitation are presented in Table II. For the images acquired after mid November 2008 precipitation data were also obtained from an automatic rain gauge (ARG) installed roughly at the center of the Zuera08 fire perimeter. Since the burned sites were located at different altitudes compared to the meteorological stations the temperatures were adjusted with the environmental lapse rate (i.e. $-2^\circ \text{ C} / 300 \text{ m}$). Accumulated precipitation (AcPp) was computed taking into account the last four days before acquisition.

C. Spectral estimates of burn severity

The dataset of reference measurements on burn severity consisted of a set of sample plots measured in the field (CBI plots) as well as pseudo-plots randomly generated using as basis the dNBR images. Although an extensive field campaign to estimate burn severity was undertaken at Zuera08 and Jaulin09 sites, it turned out that the sample population was not sufficiently dense to allow the characterization of the SAR backscatter signatures. The consistency between field and remotely sensed estimates of severity was high for Zuera08 and for Jaulin09 sites ($R^2 = 0.81$ and $R^2 = 0.83$, $p < 0.05$) supporting the decision of using dNBR as a measure of burn severity. Considering

the availability of a dNBR image for each fire and the strong correlation between CBI and dNBR, pseudo-plots of burn severity were generated by averaging pixels of similar dNBR and identical local incidence angle. Since Zuera08 and Zuera95 test sites were contiguous, and forest structure and tree species were the same, we considered appropriate to generalize the use of dNBR despite the lack of burn severity field estimates for the 1995 fire. In the study area dNBR ranged between -150 and 1050. Values up to 100 represent unburned forest whereas larger values represent increased burn severity. Similar dNBR values were obtained by reclassifying the continuous dNBR interval into twenty-four dNBR classes each being 50 units wide. To avoid bias related to size only pseudo-plots containing a large number of pixels were considered. The fixed number of pixels to be averaged implied a trade-off between the within plot variability (smaller variance for higher number of pixels per plot) and the number of pseudo-plots available for each severity level (less plots were available when higher number of pixels/plot were averaged). In the first investigation on burn severity assessment using a TerraSAR-X image nine pixel per pseudo-plot (~ 0.5 ha) appeared to be optimal for the selected spatial resolution (25 m) of the geocoded images [47]. For consistency reasons this criterion has been applied in this study as well. From the generated pseudo-plots nine hundred were randomly selected for the statistic analysis.

IV. METHODS

To understand the relationship between forest burn severity and backscatter coefficient CBI plots and dNBR base pseudo-plots were compared for Zuera08 fire. The investigation was mainly focused on Zuera08 site for which co- and cross-polarized data acquired with similar incidence angle were available at all frequencies. The Jaulin09 site was analyzed in order to confirm the trends observed at the Zuera08 site whereas the Zuera95 site was considered to evaluate the effect of different environmental conditions on the relationship between the backscatter coefficient at C-band and dNBR thanks to the large dataset of historical ERS-1/2 images available over the site (Table II).

Descriptive statistics were applied to analyze and compare backscatter as a function of burn severity. The potential of backscatter coefficient for burn severity estimation was assessed using inferential statistics. To minimize the effect of topography on the backscatter coefficient the analyses were carried out by 5° groups of local incidence angle. This interval provided optimal sampling rate for the study of the local incidence angle effects in case of TerraSAR-X data [40] so that it was used in this study as well. A higher sampling rate would have increased the data noise whereas at a lower sampling rate the topography effects would have been less evident. The homogeneity of the forest and the large extent of high burn severity allowed the evaluation of the influence of local incidence angle and weather condition on the backscatter.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Backscatter properties of burned areas

For each SAR system backscatter as a function of burn severity are presented in Fig. 3 to Fig. 6 for slopes oriented toward the sensor ($11-15^\circ$), flat or near flat areas ($21-25^\circ$) and slopes oriented away from the sensor ($36-40^\circ$). The datasets were acquired at similar look angle, around 25° . ERS SAR 1/2 VV polarized data are plotted for the Zuera95 site whereas for the Zuera08 site HH and HV polarized TerraSAR-X, ENVISAT ASAR and ALOS PALSAR data are presented. To evaluate the relationship between field- and remotely-sensed estimates of burn severity the CBI plots were also included when available. The datasets shown in Figures 3 to 6 were characterized by the largest

difference of backscatter between unburned and burned forest. Co-polarized ERS SAR and ENVISAT ASAR images were acquired under wet conditions. Co- and cross-polarized TerraSAR-X and cross-polarized ENVISAT ASAR images were acquired under dry environmental conditions. The only image available at L-band for the Zuera08 site was acquired under wet conditions. A detailed analysis of weather influence on backscatter coefficient is reported further on in this Section.

Figures 3 and 4 showed that at X- and C-band the HH co-polarized backscatter coefficient increased with burn severity at the Zuera08 site. The same trend was observed for C-band VV polarization (ERS SAR) at the Zuera95 site (Fig. 5). The tendency was found mainly for slopes facing the sensor. For slopes pointing away from the sensor the backscatter coefficient was less sensitive to changes in burn severity. Increased backscatter for the burned areas could be explained as a consequence of the weaker attenuation in the canopy due to the consumption of the needles by the fire, the subsequent exposure of the small twigs and branches with higher backscattering potential [18] and the increased backscatter from the ground. Co-polarized X- and C-band signal saturated at medium to high severity levels. The saturation level depended on the local incidence angle. It was higher for steeper slopes oriented toward the sensor due to the larger proportion of backscatter from the forest floor. Contrarily to short wavelengths L-band HH polarized backscatter decreased with the increase of burn severity especially for slopes pointing away from the sensor (Fig. 6). At L-band the radar wave is less affected by absorption and attenuation especially in low biomass forests. Thus, the scattering component from the ground does not change significantly from unburned to burned areas leaving the vegetation component as main factor determining the backscatter trend. Hence, the total backscatter is mostly a function of the crown backscatter component which decreased with increasing burn severity. The weak sensitivity of the L-band HH backscatter to burn severity for slopes facing the sensor was explained as a consequence of increased moisture due to rainfall at the time of image acquisition. The increase of backscatter due to higher soil moisture masked the effect of the burn severity for low incidence angles where the ground component plays a major role in the total backscatter.

Cross-polarized backscatter coefficient, which is sensitive primarily to volume scattering, decreased with the increase of burn severity at all frequencies (Figures 3, 4 and 6). This is explained by the smaller number of scatterers within the canopy for higher burn severity. The relatively low levels of biomass (around 45 tons/ha) resulted in a consistent trend at all local incidence angles and no evident saturation of the signal was recorded even for X-band data.

The backscatter of the CBI plots was similar to the backscatter measured at pseudo-plot level for co-polarized waves (Figures 3, 4 and 6). CBI field protocol takes into account the consumption of the attenuation layer (i.e. canopy and understory layer) thus providing indirect estimates of the increased soil exposure which explains the relatively high association to burn severity for slopes oriented to the sensor where the scattering component from the forest floor is significant. For cross-polarized waves the backscatter correspondence between CBI plots and dNBR pseudo-plots was similar only for unburned and highly burned areas. At intermediate severity levels the backscatter coefficient of the CBI plots was close to the levels registered for the unburned forest. The CBI protocol does not take into account structural modification of the crown beyond the loss of foliage. C- and X-band retained partly their sensitivity for low and intermediate CBI levels being more sensitive to small sized crown elements. On the other hand, at L-band the sensitivity to low and intermediate CBI levels decreased since no information of larger scatterers consumption was considered during the field assessment.

The trends identified at the Zuera08 site were confirmed at the Jaulin09 site. Fig. 7 presents the backscatter coefficient as a function of burn severity for flat areas at HH and HV polarization. As for the Zuera08 site, high frequency co-polarized backscatter (X- and C-band) increased whereas cross-polarized backscatter decreased with burn severity. The same decreasing trend was observed for co-polarized L-band backscatter. The similar trends suggested that radar response as a function of burn severity does not depend on the local burn conditions. In addition, the larger nominal incidence angle in the case of L-band data (see Table II) did not have a significant effect on the backscatter trends. Although, high incidence angle could cause changes in backscatter levels the sensitivity to burn severity does not seem to be affected confirming the initial results obtained with dual-polarized X-band datasets [47].

Further insight on the backscatter sensitivity to burn severity is presented in Fig. 8 which shows backscatter variation (dynamic range) from unburned to burned forest. The dynamic range was computed by taking the difference between average backscatter of adjacent unburned forest and of the burned forest. The definition of burned forest depended on the trend of the backscatter with respect to dNBR. For co-polarized data we have taken into account the saturation of the signal which depended on frequency, acquisition conditions (dry vs. wet) and the local incidence angle. Co-polarized X- and C-band saturated between 500 and 800 dNBR. Cross-polarized data did not present evident saturation and therefore the dynamic range was computed with respect to the highest severity levels recorded (950-1050 dNBR). Data acquired under wet ($AcPp > 0$) and dry conditions ($AcPp = 0$) are shown where available. The dynamic range for X- and C-band co-polarized backscatter decreased with the increasing local incidence angle from approximately 4 dB to about 1 dB which resulted in decreased sensitivity to burn severity for slopes oriented away from the sensor. The dynamic range of cross-polarized backscatter was relatively stable for all local incidence angles and decreased with the increase of SAR frequency from approximately 6 dB at L-band to around 1 dB at X-band.

The large number of ERS SAR scenes available for the Zuera95 site allowed investigating in more detail the influence of precipitation on the C-band backscatter coefficient at VV polarization, in summer and winter seasons. Higher moisture enhanced the co-polarized backscatter from the forest floor, thus increasing the dynamic range from unburned to highly burned areas at C- and X-band (Fig. 8). During summer, soil and vegetation moisture is low due to the sporadic rainfall and the high evapo-transpiration potential in the Mediterranean basin. After rainfall, soil and vegetation moisture increased which implied an increase of the backscatter coefficient. However, the increase of backscatter from unburned forest was lower (around 1 dB) than the increase for burned area (up to 6 dB depending on the local incidence angle). This explains the larger dynamic range after rainfall for acquisitions recorded during summer season. In winter, the moisture of soil and vegetation is relatively high due to the frequent rains and low evapo-transpiration. After rainfall the change of soil and vegetation water content is lower than in summer explaining the smaller variation of dynamic range from dry to wet conditions during winter season (ERS SAR 1/2 data, Fig. 8). The larger dynamic range in case of co-polarized data was observed at low local incidence angles where the contribution to the total backscatter of the ground component is largest.

To understand whether the dependence of the dynamic range on local incidence angle is related to variations of the backscatter in unburned or burned forest, in Fig. 9 mean values of the SAR backscatter are reported with respect to the local incidence angle for unburned (i.e. $dNBR < 100$) and highly burned (i.e. $dNBR \geq 600$) pseudo-plots. For increasing local incidence angle decreasing backscatter trends were registered for co-polarized waves confirming the sensitivity to ground scattering especially at steep viewing geometries. The increased backscatter observed at the largest

incidence angles for X- and C-band could be a consequence of larger vegetation contribution to the total forest backscatter [40]. The decrease of the contribution from the forest floor is smaller compared to the increase of the vegetation scattering component, thus explaining the increase of the total backscatter when compared to steeper incidence angles. In unburned areas the influence of the local incidence angle was lower since the backscatter coefficient is less dependent on the ground component due to the two-way vegetation attenuation. A slight decrease of the co-polarized backscatter was observed for the flat areas with respect to the slopes facing the sensor. Cross-polarized backscatter coefficient increased with increasing local incidence angle for all SAR frequencies (unburned and burned forests) due to the longer path traveled by the radar waves through the vegetation layer.

B. Backscatter for burn severity evaluation

To infer the utility of the backscatter for burn severity estimation, linear regression determination coefficients (R^2) expressing the proportion of burn severity variance predicted by SAR backscatter and the standard error are presented in Table III and Table IV for each sensor and polarization. A linear relation might not always represent the best fit of the data. However, this form was chosen due to the advantage of using multiple independent variables for burn severity prediction. Thus the association strength between backscatter and burn severity could be directly compared when using one or two polarizations. For multiple regression the beta standardized regression coefficients (Beta $^\circ$) have been included in Table III and Table IV for C- and L-band whereas for X-band they have been previously reported in [40]. Beta coefficients can be used to compare the relative strength of the various polarizations included in the model as well as the sign of the relationship between the SAR backscatter and burn severity when multiple channels are jointly used in the regression analysis. The statistics were computed for all 900 pseudo-plots and by local incidence angle intervals of 5°. For co-polarized ERS SAR and ENVISAT ASAR data the values are reported for images acquired under dry and wet conditions. To maximize the results wet co- and dry cross-polarized data were used for multiple regression analysis for C-band ENVISAT ASAR.

Empirical fitting showed modest relations between dNBR and the backscatter coefficient when the local incidence angle was not accounted for (Tables III and IV). After grouping by 5° intervals the association strength increased for all SAR frequencies and polarizations. The determination coefficients decreased with increasing incidence angle while the error increased for X- and C-band co-polarized images. Higher determination coefficients were obtained for ERS SAR 1/2 (1995.08.10) and ENVISAT ASAR (2009.01.08) images acquired after rainfall (Table III). However, the increase of the association strength to burn severity was not always related to rainfall. Therefore, it is difficult to predict whether images acquired under wet condition would always represent the better choice especially after heavy precipitation. L-band co-polarized data presented low association strength to burn severity for sensor oriented slopes whereas for the back-slopes the R^2 s increased (Table IV). For cross-polarized data the strength of association increased with the increase of the local incidence angle at X-band whereas at C- and L-band was relatively high over the entire range of local incidence angles. The simultaneous use of co- and cross-polarized channels provided the highest determination coefficients and the smallest errors for X- and C-band (Table III). For L-band the use of co-polarized data within a multiple regression model did not improve the determination coefficients with respect to the cross-polarized case. The high determination coefficients registered at X-band despite the smaller dynamic range are related mainly to the burn

type. The crown burn severity was highly correlated with the total plot severity. Therefore, it was feasible to estimate burn severity at plot level although the X-band is sensitive to changes in the upper part of the canopy. In addition, TerraSAR-X data were acquired at much higher spatial resolution compared to ENVISAT ASAR and ALOS PALSAR which resulted in higher ENL (see table I) which in turn increased the association strength to burn severity. This increase was previously demonstrated for the dual-polarized X-band dataset acquired over the Zuera08 site [47].

A similar analysis was carried out for the CBI plots. Nonetheless, the small number of field plots available at each local incidence angle interval, the large proportion of plots with high CBI values (see Figures 3 to 6) and the lack of detailed measurements on forest structure parameters assessed by CBI protocol implied that the statistical analysis was not sufficiently significant.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The properties of SAR backscatter in mediterranean burned forests were investigated for X-, C- and L-bands co- and cross-polarized data. The influence of the local topography and weather conditions on backscatter response was studied.

X- and C-band co-polarized backscatter increased with burn severity for slopes facing the sensor whereas for slopes pointing away from the sensor the backscatter showed no sensitivity to burn severity. L-band co-polarized backscatter showed a different behavior decreasing with increasing burn severity. Cross-polarized backscatter from burned forests was lower than for unburned forests at all SAR frequencies and the sensitivity to burn severity was rather constant over the entire range of local incidence angles. Higher moisture enhanced the co-polarized signal at X- and C-band, thus increasing the dynamic range of the backscatter between unburned and highly burned areas. Changes from very dry to wet conditions resulted in increased sensitivity of co-polarized waves to burn severity especially in summer season. However, rainfall during acquisition could diminish the sensitivity of cross-polarized data to burn severity. The local incidence angle strongly affected the backscatter coefficient from burned areas at all SAR frequencies and polarizations and its influence has to be taken into account when estimating burn severity.

At X- and C-band strong relation to burn severity was found for co-polarized waves only on slopes oriented towards the sensor whereas cross-polarized data correlated better with burn severity on the back-slopes. The highest sensitivity to burn severity was obtained for C- and L-band for which burn severity estimation was consistent using only the cross-polarized channel. The sensitivity of radar data to burn severity decreased with the increase of SAR frequency. At X-band, the lower dynamic range from unburned to burned forests was compensated by the higher spatial resolution and the combined use of co- and cross-polarized channels. However, the small dynamic range of X-band could cause difficulties for burn severity estimation.

This study indicates that SAR systems have potential for burn evaluation in mediterranean environments. Empirical modeling could be used to relate SAR data to burn severity. Nevertheless, field assessed indices should contain information on the forest structure which is the main factor influencing the backscatter. SAR data could provide more consistent estimates over the entire range of burn severities than reflectance based indices especially for cross-polarized waves and low frequencies. Although forest fires in temperate climate produce similar effects (e.g. loss of foliage, branches and the understory layer) additional data are needed to confirm these findings over mixed forests of larger biomass variability. For different environments (e.g. boreal or tropical forests) the backscatter trends from burned areas could vary since forest structure and environmental conditions are significantly different.

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Mihai A. Tanase received the engineering diploma in forestry from “Stefan cel Mare University”, Suceava, Romania in 1999, the diploma in economy from Bucharest Academy of Economic Studies, Bucharest, Romania, in 2004 and the M.Sc. degree in Environmental Management from the International Centre for Advanced Mediterranean Agronomic Studies, Paris, France, in 2007. Currently he is with the Department of Geography at the University of Zaragoza, Zaragoza, Spain. He is PI for ERS and TerraSAR-X projects and participates in K&C Initiative as co-investigator. His research includes the use of remote sensing for forest characterization. His current activity is focused on the use of SAR and interferometric SAR data for fire severity estimation and vegetation recovery monitoring after forest fires

Juan de la Riva received the PhD degree in Geography in the University of Zaragoza, Zaragoza, Spain, in 1994. He is currently a professor of Regional Geographic Analysis in the University of Zaragoza, Zaragoza, Spain. He coordinates the GIS and Remote Sensing Master Course. He focuses his research on the study of forested areas and the application of GIS and remote sensing techniques. He is member of the GEOFOREST research group and he has worked in different management studies in mountain areas, as well as in several research projects - FIRERISK, EROFUEGO, LIGNOSTRUM, RS-FIRE, PIR-FIRE – related to forest fires (post-fire environmental dynamic and risk modeling) and biomass estimation.

Maurizio Santoro (M'04) received the M.S. degree in aerospace engineering from the University "Federico II," Naples, Italy, in 1998, the Lic. Eng. degree from the Chalmers University of Technology, Göteborg, Sweden, in 2001, and the Ph.D. degree from Friedrich-Schiller-University, Jena, Germany, in 2003. From 2004 to 2005, he held a postdoctoral position at Friedrich-Schiller University. Since 2006, he has been a Project Scientist at GAMMA Remote Sensing AG, Gümligen, Switzerland. His main duties include SAR and interferometric SAR data processing, and applications of SAR interferometry for land cover mapping. He is involved as Principal and Co-Investigator in several international projects on the use of Earth observation data for land cover mapping and monitoring. His main research interests include characterization of land cover using SAR and interferometric SAR data, and retrieval techniques of forest biophysical parameters from SAR data

Thuy Le Toan received the Eng. and Ph.D. degrees in nuclear physics from the Paul Sabatier University, Toulouse, France. In 1973, she joined the Centre d'Etude Spatiale des Rayonnements, Toulouse, France, where she was Leader of the Remote Sensing Group. Since 1973, her research activity has been in the area of microwave remote sensing applied to natural surfaces. Her research interests include analysis of SAR images and experimentation and modeling of microwave interaction with agricultural and forested media. Since January 1995, she has been with the Centre d'Etudes Spatiales de la Biosphère (CESBIO), Toulouse, France. She has been a Project Coordinator and Principal Investigator on European SAR campaigns over the last decade, and was Principal Investigator of several ERS-1, ERS-2, JERS-1, SIR-C/XSAR, and RADARSAT Projects. Dr. Le Toan is a member of the ASAR Science Advisory Group (ESA) and the Electromagnetics Academy.

Fernando Pérez-Cabello received the PhD degree in Geography in the University of Zaragoza, Zaragoza, Spain, in 2001. He is currently a professor contracted doctor of Regional Geographic Analysis in the University of Zaragoza, Zaragoza, Spain. He focused his research on the analysis of the environmental dynamic of burned areas, by means of field data and remote sensing and GIS techniques. He is member of the GEOFOREST research group and he has worked at some national research projects - FIRERISK, EROFUEGO, LIGNOSTRUM, RS-FIRE, PIR-FIRE – concerning to the monitoring of burned areas, fire risk cartography and modeling of physical variables.

Table I
SAR data characteristics and processing parameters

Satellite/Parameter	PALSAR	PALSAR	ERS 1 / 2	ASAR	ASAR	ASAR	TSX
Band [wavelength cm]	L- [23.6]	L- [23.6]	C- [5.7]	C- [5.7]	C- [5.7]	C- [5.7]	X- [3.1]
Pass	ascending	ascending	descending	descending	ascending	descending	descending
Acquisition mode	PLR	FBD	-	IM	IM	AP	SM
Incidence angle	26°	39°	23°	23°	23°	23°	26°/40°
Polarization	HH,VV,HV,VH	HH,HV	VV	HH	VV	HH,HV	HH,HV
Range pixel spacing (m)	9.4	9.4	12.5	7.8	12.5	12.5	0.9
Azimuth pixel spacing (m)	3.8	3.2	12.5	4.0	12.5	12.5	2.2
Multi-look factor (range/azimuth)	1/7	2/10	2 / 2	1 / 5	2 / 2	2 / 2	17/10
Data format	SLC	SLC	PRI	SLC	PRI	PRI	SLC
Pixel spacing (map geometry)	25 m	25 m	25 m	25 m	25 m	25 m	25 m
Equivalent number of looks	11	22	12	4	12	6	50/55
Geolocation error	~2 m	~ 2 m	~ 2.5 m	~ 2.5 m	~ 2.5 m	~ 2.5 m	~ 0.75 m
Projection / Ellipsoid Datum	Universal Transverse Mercator, Zone 30 / International 1924 European 1950						

Table II
SAR acquisitions and climate data (AcPp in mm and Tmax. and Tmin. in °C)

Sensor and polarization	Mode	Date	AcPp	Tmax	Tmin	Sensor and polarization	Mode	Date	AcPp	Tmax	Tmin
ERS-1 VV ^a	IM	1992.08.31 ¹	0	24	13	ASAR VV ^b	IM	2008.09.12	1.6	18	11
ERS-1 VV ^a	IM	1995.07.05	0	26	11	ASAR HH ^b	IM	2009.01.08	0.5	0	-6
ERS-2 VV ^a	IM	1995.08.10	6.5*	29	16	ASAR HH ^b	IM	2009.02.12	0.5*	10	4
ERS-2 VV ^a	IM	1995.09.14	0	23	9	ASAR HH, HV ^b	AP	2009.03.19	0	20	-1
ERS-2 VV ^a	IM	2008.06.12 ¹	-	-	-	ASAR HH, HV ^c	AP	2009.09.29	5*	22	11
ERS-2 VV ^a	IM	2008.08.21	0	30	15	TSX HH,HV ^b	SM	2008.11.16	0	14	-2
ERS-1 VV ^a	IM	1995.12.14	0	4	-4	TSX HH,HV ^b	SM	2008.12.19	0	11	4
ERS-2 VV ^v	IM	1995.12.15	2.7*	0	-5	TSX HH,HV ^b	SM	2008.12.24 ²	0	-3	-6
ERS-2 VV ^a	IM	1996.01.19	1*	10	-2	TSX HH,HV ^b	SM	2009.01.21	2.3	7	-3
ERS-1 VV ^a	IM	1996.03.28	0	15	5	TSX HH,HV ^b	SM	2009.02.12	0.5*	10	4
ERS-2 VV ^a	IM	1996.03.29	0	17	6	TSX HH,HV ^b	SM	2009.02.23	0	12	5
ERS-1 VV ^a	IM	1995.11.28	0	12	-4	TSX HH,HV ^b	SM	2009.03.06	11.8*	9	1
ERS-1 VV ^a	IM	1996.01.02	4.5	11	4	TSX HH, HV ^c	SM	2009.09.20	5	20	8
ERS-2 VV ^a	IM	1996.01.03	1.5	11	0	PALSAR ^b	PLR	2009.04.28	3.5*	18	10
ASAR VV ^b	IM	2008.07.04 ¹	0	31	8	PALSAR ^c	FBD	2009.10.05 ³	0	28	10

1 acquired before fire // 2 data acquired at 25° look angle // 3 data acquired at 34° look angle // * precipitations registered partially during the day of SAR acquisition // a Zuer95 // b Zuer08 // c Janlin09

Table III
Determination coefficients explaining the agreement between burn severity expressed as dNBR and C-band backscatter

Sensor	C-Band ERS-1/2				C-band ASAR									
	VV		VV		HH		HH		HV		HH&HV		HH&HV	
Scene date	1995.07.05	1995.08.10	2009.03.19	2009.01.08	2009.03.19	2009.01.08	2009.03.19	2009.01.08	2009.03.19	2009.01.08	2009.03.19	Beta°	Beta°	
	R ²	Std. err.	R ²	Std. err.	HH	HV								
all pseudo-plots	0.020	261.7	0.127	247.0	0.013	344.5	0.172	327.9	0.493	256.6	0.542	252.1	0.149	-0.640
pseudo-plots grouped by local incidence angle														
6-10	0.442	201.6	0.677	153.2	0.466	299.4	0.768	197.1	0.779	192.5	0.894	135.2	0.491	-0.528
10-15	0.246	214.8	0.556	164.8	0.117	334.0	0.555	234.6	0.660	207.2	0.782	167.1	0.434	-0.554
16-20	0.128	223.0	0.505	168.0	0.195	316.9	0.449	257.6	0.592	225.7	0.760	173.7	0.442	-0.606
21-25	0.005	259.6	0.248	225.7	0.053	3339	0.354	269.4	0.621	211.2	0.684	193.5	0.280	-0.664
26-30	0.004	266.5	0.162	244.5	0.008	338.0	0.198	303.2	0.481	244.6	0.542	230.5	0.258	-0.623
31-35	0.013	261.3	0.064	254.5	0.008	342.2	0.154	321.4	0.653	202.3	0.682	194.4	0.179	-0.758
36-40	0.143	250.7	0.001	270.7	0.009	368.8	0.174	330.9	0.694	204.9	0.722	196.3	0.178	-0.771
41-45	0.001	292.0	0.010	290.5	0.120	357.9	0.109	361.9	0.704	207.5	0.729	199.6	0.161	-0.807

Table IV
Determination coefficients explaining the agreement between burn severity expressed as dNBR and X- and L-band backscatter

Sensor	X-band TerraSAR-X						L-band PALSAR							
Polariz.	HH		HV		HH & HV		HH		HV		HH & HV			
Scene	2008.12.24						2009.04.28							
	R^2	Std. err.	R^2	Std. err.	R^2	Std. err.	R^2	Std. err.	R^2	Std. err.	R^2	Std. err.	Beta° HH	Beta° HV
all pseudo-plots	0.425	273.3	0.162	330.0	0.478	260.6	0.054	345.9	0.692	197.3	0.693	200.2	-0.046	-0.821
pseudo-plots grouped by local incidence angle														
6-10	0.734	201.7	0.173	355.5	0.890	131.5	0.029	401.2	0.845	160.2	0.869	148.8	0.153	-9.916
10-15	0.714	196.3	0.510	257.0	0.915	107.5	0.028	379.8	0.833	157.3	0.862	143.7	0.170	-0.913
16-20	0.586	225.1	0.331	286.1	0.836	142.3	0.001	363.4	0.858	136.9	0.862	135.8	0.061	-0.929
21-25	0.681	198.4	0.231	308.3	0.843	139.6	0.093	331.9	0.861	130.2	0.861	130.7	0.005	-0.929
26-30	0.374	269.6	0.387	266.6	0.742	173.6	0.274	293.7	0.841	137.6	0.841	138.0	0.024	-0.931
31-35	0.370	274.2	0.525	238.0	0.783	161.7	0.623	214.9	0.829	144.8	0.829	145.3	-0.020	-0.893
36-40	0.555	242.0	0.654	213.4	0.812	158.3	0.703	185.8	0.822	143.7	0.822	144.3	-0.004	-0.904
41-45	0.544	245.7	0.665	210.4	0.831	150.4	0.779	165.7	0.876	124.1	0.883	121.3	-0.197	-0.758
46-50	0.562	262.1	0.805	175.0	0.897	128.1	0.764	158.2	0.853	124.9	0.867	120.7	-0.257	-0.696
51-55	0.598	238.9	0.805	166.3	0.895	125.3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Fig. 1 The study area and the forest fire sites. The burn severity expressed by dNBR index was overlaid on a RGB composite of pre-fire Landsat TM images (2008.07.21 and 2009.06.22)

Fig.2 Zuera08 fire scar as revealed by TerraSAR-X, ENVISAT ASAR and ALOS PALSAR (red: HH backscatter, green: HV backscatter, blue: HH/HV backscatter ratio)

Fig. 3 Backscatter (γ^0) with respect to burn severity for X-band HH (top) and HV (bottom) for the Zuera08 site (TerraSAR-X, 2008.12.24) for slopes oriented towards the sensor (left), flat areas (center) and slopes oriented away from the sensor (right). Circles refer to dNBR measurements. Filled circles refer to CBI measurements.

Fig. 4 Scatter plots of C-band HH (top) and HV (bottom) backscatter with respect to burn severity (dNBR) for the Zuera08 site (ENVISAT ASAR 2009.01.08 - HH and 2009.03.19 - HV images). Left slopes oriented towards sensor, center flat areas, right slopes oriented away from the sensor. Circles refer to dNBR measurements. Filled circles refer to CBI measurements.

Fig. 5 Backscatter (γ^0) with respect to burn severity (dNBR) for C-band VV backscatter for the Zuera95 site (ERS-2, 1995.08.10) for slopes oriented towards the sensor (left), flat areas (center) and slopes oriented away from the sensor (right).

Fig. 6 Backscatter (γ^0) with respect to burn severity for L-band HH (top) and HV (bottom) for the Zuera08 site (ALOS PALSAR, 2009.04.28) for slopes oriented towards the sensor (left), flat areas (center) and slopes oriented away from the sensor (right). Circles refer to dNBR measurements. Filled circles refer to CBI measurements.

Fig. 7 Average normalized backscatter coefficient (γ^0) for X-, C- and L-band, at HH and HV polarization for the Jaulin09 site (flat areas). TerraSAR-X 2009.09.20 (left), ENVISAT ASAR 2009.09.29 (center) and ALOS PALSAR 2009.10.05 (right).

Fig. 8 Dynamic range of backscatter with respect to local incidence angle. The filled markers refer to data acquired under wet conditions

Fig. 9 Average normalized backscatter coefficient (γ^0) with respect to local incidence angle for unburned (top) and highly burned pseudo-plots (bottom)